

ON THE CONSTITUTION OF ERDMANN'S SALT. PART I.

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As early as 1866 Erdmann described the ammonium tetranitro-diammine cobaltate in which the two ammonium groups might have taken the two adjacent or remote positions yielding in the first case a 'cis' and in the second a 'trans' compound. The problem of determining the constitution of Erdmann's salt was taken up by Shibata and Maruki (*J. Coll. Sci. Imp. Univ. Tokio*, 1917, 41, No. 2, 1). They prepared the oxalato-dinitro-diammine cobaltate according to the method of Jorgensen. Theoretically this compound may have any of the following three constitutions.

Shibata and Maruki (*loc. cit.*) claimed to have resolved the oxalato-dinitro-diammine salt, a fact from which it follows that (I) is its constitutional formula. Riesenfeld and Klement undertook the problem but could not resolve the compound. From this fact, as also from other chemical reactions they decided the original Erdmann's salt to have a *trans*-ammonia constitution (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1922, 125, 1). Thomas (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 617), however, prepared the oxalato-dinitro-diammine complex and, by fractional crystallisation separated two sets of crystals, (i) rhombohedral, the less soluble variety and (ii) monoclinic, the more soluble one. Thomas resolved the rhombohedral variety into its optical antipodes but could not separate the solid active form. The monoclinic variety could not be resolved and Thomas (*loc. cit.*) quite arbitrarily represented it by (III), without considering the possibility of the formation of (II).

In view of the contradictory statements regarding the resolvability of the oxalato-dinitro-diammine cobaltate the works of the earlier authors were closely repeated. But neither the rhombohedral nor the monoclinic variety was found to be resolvable. Besides, the potassium salt from both

the varieties on treatment with ethylenediamine, yielded the same insoluble non-electrolyte. This, however, supports Riesenfeld's view.

As a result of the study of absorption spectra, it has been generalised that where there is a pair of *trans*-nitro group in the cobaltamine complex, three distinct absorption bands appear in the spectrum at about 2000, 3000 and 4000 frequencies (expressed in terms of wave-number per mm.). The *cis*-nitro complexes, however, lack in the band at extreme ultra-violet the frequency of 4000 (Shibata, *J. Coll. Sci. Imp. Univ. Tokio*, 1915, 37, No. 2, x). The structure of the monoclinic variety was attempted to be determined from the standpoint of the above generalisation. It has been found to have a *cis*-nitro-*trans*-ammonia constitution like (II) (*vide* experimental).

From a careful consideration of the spectrographic and chemical evidences it appears that both rhombohedral as also the monoclinic varieties have identical structures, namely the *cis*-nitro and *trans*-ammonia groupings. The two sets of crystals would then indicate the allotropic modifications of the oxalato-dinitro-diammine cobaltiate. Thus assuming that during reactions no rearrangement of groups takes place, it can be well inferred that the original Erdmann salt is a *trans*-ammonia-*cis*-nitro compound and should be represented as :

(IV)

From measurements of crystal structure of the silver tetranitrodiammine cobaltiate by the X-ray method, Wells has shown recently that the two ammonia groups are in the *trans*-position (*Z. Krist.*, 1936, 95, 74).

E X P E R I M E N T A L .

Barium Oxalato-dinitrodiammine Cobaltiate.—Two samples of ammonium oxalato-dinitro-diammine cobaltiate were prepared separately according to the methods of (i) Jorgensen (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1896, 11, 440) and (ii) Riesenfeld and Klement (*loc. cit.*). The hot saturated solution of the

ammonium salt was then treated with calculated quantity of barium chloride. On stirring the barium salt separated out. It was filtered, washed and recrystallised from water several times.

Fractional Crystallisation of the Barium Salt.—The barium salts were both subjected to fractional crystallisation whence a rhombohedral set of crystals formed the head and the monoclinic the tail fractions.

Reaction of Potassium Salt with Ethylenediamine.—To a solution of both the rhombohedral and monoclinic variety of the potassium salt, obtained from barium salt by treating the latter with potassium sulphate, ethylenediamine (just sufficient to replace the two ammonia molecules) was added. The solution was heated on a water-bath until the evolution of ammonia ceased. Insoluble brown precipitates containing ethylenediamine, nitrous acid; ammonia and cobaltic cobalt separated from both the rhombohedral as also the monoclinic variety. The salts were separately analysed and found to be identical. (Found: Co, 21.57; C_2O_4 , 15.9. Reisenfeld and Klement's $Co_2En_3(NO_2)_4(NH_3)_2 C_2O_4$ requires Co, 21.69; C_2O_4 , 16.17 per cent).

Preparation of Strychnine Salt and Polarimetric Observation.—The barium salts of the complex cobaltates were separately converted into strychnine sulphate and in each case the products were collected fractionally. Pure analysed samples of the strychnine salts of different fractions were tested in a polarimeter. Every sample gave exactly the same value for specific rotation (1% soln. in a 2 dm. tube $[\alpha]_D^{25}$, -42.5). These different samples of strychnine salts were next treated with potassium iodide and after separation of strychnine iodide, the pure potassium salt was isolated (2 dm. of 1% solution of the potassium salt gave no rotation at all when tested polarimetrically).

Preparation of the Compound $l-[CoEn_3][Co(NO_2)_2C_2O_4(NH_3)_2]$, $6H_2O$.—To a saturated solution of the oxalato-dinitro-diammine cobaltate was added a concentrated solution of the calculated quantity of *laevo* $(CoEn_3) Br_3, 2H_2O$. Immediate precipitation of *l*- $CoEn_3, Co(NO_2)_2, C_2O_4(NH_3)_2, 6H_2O$ occurred. The precipitate was filtered, washed, and recrystallised from hot water. (Found: Co, 20.31; NH_3 , 8.71; Total N, 21.66. Calc.: Co, 20.24; NH_3 , 8.74; Total N, 21.61 per cent.).

Polarimetric Investigation of the Salt.—The triethylenediammine base was precipitated with the help of a calculated quantity of $Na_5 \left[Co \begin{matrix} (SO_3)_2 \\ (CN)_4 \end{matrix} \right]$. $12H_2O$ and the precipitate immediately filtered by low suction. The residue was repeatedly washed with water, the filtrate and subsequent washings being collected in a measuring flask. The solution having a

theoretical concentration of 1% was tested in a 2 dm. tube polarimetrically. Absolutely no rotation could be detected.

Constitution of the Monoclinic variety of Oxalato-dinitro-diammine Cobaltiate from Spectrographic Evidences.—For comparing the validity of Shibata's generalisation with regard to the position of absorption maxima and the nitro groups, the ultra-violet absorption of the Flavo, Croceo and sodium cobaltinitrite etc., have been studied, in addition to those of the rhombohedral and monoclinic varieties of the oxalato-dinitro complexes.

Conc. = $N/10,000$. Time of exposure = 20 sec. for soln. ; 10 sec. for arc ;
5 sec. for scale.

Arc used—Iron Arc.

(Observations made by varying the length of columns in Baly's Tube)

Substance.	Absorption band between.	Wave-number per mm.	Substance.	Absorption band between.	Wave-number per mm.
Na-cobaltinitrite	2640-2650Å	3781	Erdmann's salt	2430-2450Å	4099
	3320-3350	2999		3320-3350	2999
	4700-4800	2105		4650-4700	2139
<i>cis</i> -Dinitro-tetrammine	Absent		Oxalato-dinitro-diammine (prepared according to Riesenfeld's method)	Absent	
	3320-3350	2990		3320-3350	2999
	4650-4700	2139		4700-4800	2103
<i>trans</i> -Dinitro-tetrammine	2430-2450	4099	Oxalato-dinitro-diammine (rhombohedral)	Absent	
	3320-3340	3003		3320-3350	2999
	4650-4700	2139	4700-4800	2103	
			Oxalato-dinitro diammine (monoclinic)	Absent	
			3320-3350	2999	
			4700-4800	2103	

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